

DRONE SURVEYING FOR THE RESTORATION OF HISTORIC BUILDINGS

NENAD GALJAK¹, JELENA KOLOROGIĆ², SLAĐANA STANIŠIĆ³, MIROSLAV VUJASINOVIĆ⁴, MIODRAG REGODIĆ⁵

¹ University of Defence, Military Academy, Belgrade, galjaknenad@gmail.com, 0000-0002-2493-9202

² University of Banja Luka, Faculty of Architecture, Civil Engineering and Geodesy, Banja Luka, jelena.kolorogic@student.aggf.unibl.org, 0009-0007-3790-001X

³ University of Banja Luka, Faculty of Architecture, Civil Engineering and Geodesy, Banja Luka; sladjana.stanisic@aggf.unibl.org, 0009-0002-3148-6819

⁴ University of Banja Luka, Faculty of Architecture, Civil Engineering and Geodesy, Banja Luka, miroslav.vujasinovic@aggf.unibl.org, 0009-0008-0398-5614

⁵ University of Banja Luka, Faculty of Architecture, Civil Engineering and Geodesy, Banja Luka, miodrag.regodic@aggf.unibl.org, 0000-0003-4675-4150

Abstract: *Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), thanks to the rapid development of sensors, software, and communication and navigation technologies, have become economically very accessible and easy to use, which has opened up great possibilities for their application. UAVs have become an excellent platform for collecting spatial data, which can be used to create 3D models of terrain or objects. With the help of appropriate technology, it is possible to achieve the preservation, protection, and valorization of architectural, archaeological, and all other forms of cultural heritage. Photogrammetry is a scientific field that plays a very important role in documenting cultural and historical heritage. This paper presents the method of data collection using a UAV, as well as the process of data processing and modeling. The imagery obtained by using the UAV was processed, a digital model of the building was created, and the modeling procedure was described.*

Keywords: *Historical structures, Unmanned aerial vehicle, Terrestrial photogrammetry, Digital building model.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The continuous advancement of computer technology and its increasing availability have led to a growing demand for high-quality geospatial data. Due to their complexity and diversity, primarily in geometric terms, an increasing amount of measured data is required for accurate and detailed representation. One of the most efficient methods currently used for collecting data in the field includes photogrammetry and laser scanning techniques.

Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) have become excellent platforms for collecting spatial data, which can be used to create 3D models of terrain or objects. UAVs can be remotely controlled, automated, or autonomous systems capable of gathering large amounts of data in a short period of time. Thanks to the rapid development of sensors, software, and communication and navigation technologies, they have become economically accessible and easy to use. This has resulted in an increasing number of potential applications.

The use of photogrammetry in the preservation of historical structures has a very long tradition. Photogrammetric measurements have been used for decades to create documentation of historical buildings and assist in their restoration.

2. APPLICATION OF CLOSE-RANGE PHOTOGRAMMETRY FOR THE PURPOSE OF CREATING GEODETIC-TECHNICAL DOCUMENTATION OF OBJECTS

The purpose of creating geodetic-technical documentation is to appropriately document the existing geometric condition of the object. The goal can be inspection of the object, preparation of bases for reconstruction and rehabilitation, harmonization of new objects with the existing environment, or the creation of technical documentation for archival purposes.

The emergence of digital photogrammetry has opened up entirely new possibilities in the creation of geodetic-technical documentation for building structures. The changes are very significant and relate not only to the existing work phases, such as:

- surveying;
- preparation of graphic documentation;
- archiving;
- creation of digital orthophotos and 3D models of objects.

The process of creating geodetic-technical documentation is divided into two logical phases. The first consists of photogrammetric surveying, necessary field measurements, and preparation of archival documentation. The second phase involves the creation of detailed geometric documentation, such as precise digital orthophotos, 2D or 3D models of the object, and similar, all in digital form.

2.1. Digital Building Model

Digital Building Model - DBM is created by collecting data about constructed structures and can be described as a set of individual 3D objects that are not interconnected. (Cetl, Tomić & Lisjak, 2013).

Figure 1: Digitalbuilding model(DJI, 2025)

Digital models (3D models) are created based on spatial data obtained using various geodetic methods. In addition to data collection using unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), data for the creation of 3D models can also be obtained using the following methods:

- field geodetic surveys;
- laser scanning;
- radar data acquisition;
- vectorization method using existing topographic bases (Lukić, Terzić, Galjak, Gigović, Stojanović & Kremlić, 2024).

2.2. Restoration of historical buildings

With the emergence of photogrammetric surveying, this discipline has assumed a crucial role in documenting cultural and historical heritage.

Monuments and historical buildings are the most reliable records of history. They are of immeasurable value, but every structure has its lifespan and ages along with the materials from which it was built (even under ideal conditions).

For culturally and historically significant structures, there are various types of documentation, which also represent one of the first steps in the preservation of cultural heritage. These usually include documents related to geometry, landscape, archaeology, construction materials, and the historical and cultural significance of the site, among others. During the process of documentation and recording, knowledge about the structures can be expanded based on old photographs, drawings, and plans, state archives, archaeological data, and notes.(Mulahusić, Tuno, Topoljak, Balić, Hadžiosmanović, Stanić, & Hajdar, 2013).

Photogrammetric surveys have been used for the documentation of historical structures and their restoration over many years.

3. AERIAL SURVEYING OF HERITAGE STRUCTURES USING UNMANNED AERIAL VEHICLES FOR RESTORATION APPLICATIONS

The practical part of the work consists of surveying the structure using the photogrammetric method (close-range photogrammetry) and subsequent modeling aimed at the restoration of the building's facade.

The surveying and modeling were carried out on a section of the City Administration building of the City of Banja Luka (Figure 3), which represents one of the most significant structures in terms of cultural development, as well as in the study of architectural heritage in Yugoslavia. The construction of the Ban's Administration building lasted from August 27, 1930, until the autumn of 1931. The greatest damage to the building and its interior occurred during World War II and the 1969 earthquake. The restoration of the building was carried out in 1972, based on the original project documentation. (Vidaković, 2006).

3.1. Unmanned Aerial Vehicle DJI Phantom 4 Pro

European Aviation Safety Agency - EASA defines an unmanned aerial vehicle as an aircraft without a pilot, whose flight is controlled either autonomously or remotely by a pilot on the ground or in another vehicle.

Figure 2: Unmanned Aerial Vehicle DJI Phantom 4 Pro (DJI, 2025)

The DJI Phantom 4 Pro quadcopter can reach a maximum speed of up to 72 km/h in Sport mode, with continuous operation lasting up to 30 minutes, and a maximum altitude of 6,000 meters (DJI, 2025).

The Phantom 4 Pro quadcopter is equipped with a one-inch 20 MP sensor, offering a dynamic range of nearly 12 stops. The video capability is also 4K, utilizing the H.265 codec, allowing for fast and efficient processing – 4096 x 2160 at 50 fps and 3840 x 2160 at 60 fps, both at 100 Mbps (with the H.264 codec, 4K video can reach up to 60 fps). (DJI, 2025).

3.2. Data Collection and Processing

The structure was photographed from approximately equal distances (due to the manual operation of the drone) to ensure minimal lateral and longitudinal overlap (60% longitudinal and 30% lateral) between two images. The captured images are in JPG format, and the coordinates of the control points are in a .txt file. Data processing was carried out using the 3D modeling software AgiSoft Metashape Professional.

The final result of the processing is a photorealistic 3D model that can be further used for various purposes: GIS, cultural heritage documentation, visual effects production, or indirect measurements of structures.

First, it is necessary to load and then align the photographs. The software searches for common points in the images, overlaps them, determines the camera position for each photo, and calculates the camera calibration parameters. As a result, a sparse point cloud is generated, which in this case consists of a total of 220,955 points. The sparse point cloud represents the outcome of the image alignment process and is not directly used in the subsequent steps of 3D model creation.

Based on the sparse point cloud, a dense point cloud is generated. Using the estimated camera positions and images, the software automatically creates the dense point cloud (Figure 3). The dense point cloud consists of 28,541,718 points. After that, the point cloud is georeferenced using ground control points.

Figure 3: Dense point cloud

A dense point cloud was used to create a digital elevation model, which was then used to generate an orthophoto or orthomosaic. The surveying and modeling were performed on a section of the City Administration building in Banja Luka, which is considered one of the most significant structures for the study of architectural heritage in Yugoslavia. (Figures 4 and 5).

Figure 4: Digital elevation model and digital orthophoto

Figure 5: Detail of the building facade shown as an orthomosaic

Based on the generated and processed dense point cloud in Agisoft Metashape Professional, a 3D polygon mesh is reconstructed to represent the surface of the object. Generally, two algorithmic methods can be applied for mesh generation: Height Field – for flat surfaces, and Arbitrary – for all types of objects. Both methods use the dense point cloud as the basis, while the sparse point cloud is used for faster generation. The resulting geometric reconstruction can be textured or used to generate textures or orthophotos in further processing. The software SketchUp was used to create the 3D model of the building facade.

Figure 6: Modeling the Facade of the Ban's Administration Building in SketchUp

In order to improve the visualization, the facade of the City Administration building in Banja Luka was rendered using the Enscape software solution. Rendering, as a final process, represents a consistent conversion of three-dimensional models into two-dimensional images. The following images show the final result of the restoration of the building. (Figures 7 and 8).

Figure 7: Rendered 3D model of the facade

Figure 8: Details of the 3D model of the facade

4. CONCLUSION

Thanks to the ease of data collection using unmanned aerial vehicles, it is now possible to survey areas of interest at any time, as well as measure hard-to-reach building elements, which is a significant advantage over traditional surveying methods. Additionally, the application of this technology leads to a considerable reduction in project costs.

One of the most efficient methods of data collection in the field used today are photogrammetry and laser scanning techniques.

The data processing workflow is user-friendly and fully automated. The software allows for editing and removal of unwanted objects, as well as the creation of additional products such as orthophoto maps, orthophoto facades, vectorization of characteristic lines, point clouds, digital models, and more.

Based on the point cloud generated from drone images, detailed and up-to-date bases for modeling the current state of structures can be obtained. The modeling and visualization of the facade for the purpose of its restoration are successfully carried out using the obtained digital building model, point cloud, and orthophoto. Additionally, the resulting model is suitable for inclusion in any existing 3D registry (3D cadastre, BIM, virtual 3D city model) and can be used in virtual and augmented reality applications.

In the field of large-scale data collection, drone surveying technology is undoubtedly becoming the technology of the future. This technology enables geodesy to expand the scope of its activities and successfully collaborate with other disciplines.

LITERATURE

- Cetl, V., Tomić, H., & Lisjak, J. (2013). *Application of 3D City Model in Spatial Planning of the City of Zagreb*. Zagreb.
- DJI. (2025). *DJI Phantom 4 Pro*. Retrieved from <https://pcfoto.biz/dji-phantom-4-pro.html>
- Inc., 3D model – SketchUp 3D Warehouse. Retrieved from 2025 [sahttps://3dwarehouse.sketchup.com/warehouse/v1.0/content/public/1da022b0-856f-4b06-8563-f5c7fd344165](https://3dwarehouse.sketchup.com/warehouse/v1.0/content/public/1da022b0-856f-4b06-8563-f5c7fd344165).
- Lukić, D., Terzić, M., Galjak, N., Gigović, Lj., Stojanović, M., & Kremić, Ž. (2024). *GIS multicriteria model of paths planning for potential mini-UAV attacks*, 472-479, Zlatibor, doi: 10.5937/KonGef24052L.
- Mulahusić, A., Tuno, N., Topoljak, J., Balić, D., Hadžiosmanović, E., Stanić, S., & Hajdar, A. (2013). *Application of Photogrammetry and Laser Scanning in Protecting the Cultural and Historical Heritage*, 47(44), 34–57. doi:10.58817/2233-1786.2013.47.44.34
- Vidaković, S. (2006). Buildings of the Ban's Court and Administration. In *Architecture of Public Buildings in Banja Luka (1918–1941)* (str. 36–51). Banja Luka: Academy of Arts RS Banja Luka.